

1. **DATA SUMMARY**

DOI	Name of the dataset	Work Package (Task)		
10.5281/zenodo.115470	D1.4 Preparatory Actions Report	WP1		
Principal type of data contained in the data set				
☐ Quantitative ☐ Qualitative ☒ Numeric ☐ Text ☐ Images ☐ Audio ☐ Video ☒ Databases ☐ Non-structured data ☐ Source code ☐ Computational models ☐ Time series ☒ Other (please specify): Vector data				
Data description				
Please, describe the data to be collected. Please specify the type and provide a short description of every field contained in the data. Moreover, add information about the size of the data set, format, etc. Information retrieved to monitoring the KPIs. Its contains: * Spatial database formed by a set vector data in shapefile format. * Tabular Information about the state of the waste management system in all the pilot sites				
What is the source of the data?				
☒ Field work ☒ Direct measurements ☐ Surveys ☒ Simulations ☐ Expert Knowledge, ☐ Model Output ☒ Other (please specify): Data Estimation, Oficial Databases				
Methodology used to collect this data				
Please briefly describe the processes or methods which have been used to get the data. Waste generation: filling sensors, data estimation, field work Route: GPS, digitalization, simulation Deposit point: GPS, field work				
Relation to the data with the objectives of the project				
☒ Reduce the generation of RSU. ☒ Increase the management of waste in favour of reusing and recycling. ☒ Reduce the waste to landfill. ☒ Reduce the management cost. ☒ Reduce the generation of GHG emissions. ☐ Other (please specify): KPIs monitoring for the data calculation				
Relation to the data with the results of the project				
<table border="0"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top;"> <u>Operation and Planning:</u> ☒ Operation and Management Module. ☒ Collection Module. ☒ Planning Module. ☒ Circular Economy Module. <u>APPs:</u> ☒ Food App. ☒ Local Trade App. ☒ Citizen App. <u>Educational Materials:</u> ☒ Innovative Teaching Units. ☒ Sorting Game. ☒ Eco-design Game. ☒ Planning Game. ☒ Virtual City Game. </td> <td style="vertical-align: top;"> <u>Citizen Science:</u> ☒ Eco-design solutions. ☒ Planning solutions. ☒ Circular economy solutions. <u>Prevention and Best Practices:</u> ☒ Economic instruments: New Pay-As-you-Throw (PAYT) schemes and incentives. ☒ Innovative awareness actions including web-based tools for dissemination. ☒ Best Practice Book. <u>New Treatments:</u> ☒ Pre-dried and shredded bio-waste. ☒ Bio-fuel and compost production plant.# </td> </tr> </table>			<u>Operation and Planning:</u> ☒ Operation and Management Module. ☒ Collection Module. ☒ Planning Module. ☒ Circular Economy Module. <u>APPs:</u> ☒ Food App. ☒ Local Trade App. ☒ Citizen App. <u>Educational Materials:</u> ☒ Innovative Teaching Units. ☒ Sorting Game. ☒ Eco-design Game. ☒ Planning Game. ☒ Virtual City Game.	<u>Citizen Science:</u> ☒ Eco-design solutions. ☒ Planning solutions. ☒ Circular economy solutions. <u>Prevention and Best Practices:</u> ☒ Economic instruments: New Pay-As-you-Throw (PAYT) schemes and incentives. ☒ Innovative awareness actions including web-based tools for dissemination. ☒ Best Practice Book. <u>New Treatments:</u> ☒ Pre-dried and shredded bio-waste. ☒ Bio-fuel and compost production plant.#
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Why is this data collected?				
Please, contextualize the information collected. This information is needed to KPIs monitoring for the data calculation . Control and monitoring of project objectives				
Please, provide a brief description of any external dataset used				
For every external data set used please explain its origin, relevance and license. Official databases				

2. FAIR DATA (DATA FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSE)

2.1. DATA FINDABLE

Tim's 5-star classification of the dataset	
☐ Data is available under an open license ☒ Use a structured data (e.g., Excel instead of image scan of a table) ☒ Is available in a non-proprietary open format (e.g., CSV as well as of Excel) ☐ Use URIs to denote things ☐ The data is linked to other data to provide context	
Metadata standards	
<p>Please cite the standard and format use for the data. If any this data set does not follow any standardized format, please provide a formal specification. For example, the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, Inspire Initiative, ISO, etc.</p> <p>Inspire Initiative</p> <p>Link regarding to metadata standard: http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/</p>	
Documentation stored in the data	
☒ Information of the origin of the data ☐ Codebook ☐ List of abbreviations	☒ Description of variables ☒ Technical information about files ☐ Other (please specify):
Ontologies	
☐ FIWARE Link regarding to fiware https://www.fiware.org/data-models	☐ Other external ontology Link regarding to ontologies https://www.w3.org/wiki/Lists_of_ontologies ☐ Our defined ontology (please specify):
Whom might it be useful?	
☒ Public Administrations ☒ Research groups ☒ Citizens	☒ Private sector ☐ Other (please specify):
Channels to reach potential users	
☐ Personal/research group web page ☐ Well-known specialist database ☐ Search Administration database ☒ Email of corresponding author	☐ Data access statement in published articles ☐ Personal networking ☒ Citation of data sets ☒ Other (please specify): Waste4Think website Zenodo

2.2. DATA ACCESSIBLE

Accessibility	
☒ Public data	☐ Confidential data
Obligation or intention to publish/share data	
☒ Yes	☐ No
When will the data be published?	
☐ Immediately on collection ☐ Within sometime after the ends of the project (please specify): ☐ Within sometime after its collection (please specify):	☒ To coincide with publication of main results ☐ Other (please specify): Publication of Deliverable D1.4
Expected difficulties file sharing	
☐ Confidentiality ☐ Large file size ☐ Ownership/licensing	☐ Intended commercialisation ☐ Other (please specify): None

2.3. DATA INTEROPERABLE

File format			
<u>Spreadsheet:</u> ☐ ODS ☒ XLS ☐ CSV <u>Documentation</u> ☐ DOC ☐ PDF ☐ TXT ☐ HTML	<u>Structured data</u> ☐ XML ☐ JSON <u>Geographical data</u> ☐ DXF ☒ SHP ☐ GEOJSON	<u>Image:</u> ☐ JPG ☐ TIFF ☐ PNG <u>Video:</u> ☐ WEBM ☐ MP4 ☐ MKZ	<u>Other</u> (please specify):
Methods or software tools needed to access the data			
Please detail any necessary software to manipulate the information (if not standard). Geographic information system (GIS) SpreadSheet software able to open xls files			

2.4. DATA REUSE

License conditions and restrictions	
☐ Copyright ☐ Creative Commons (please specify)	☒ Open Licence (please specify): ☐ Other (please specify):
Please, list the owners of the copyright and intellectual property involved	
The authors of the document. Public Authorities. OpenStreetMap contributors	
Access permissions and restrictions	
List roles/individuals (internal & external) with any limitations to access (e.g. scope, actions permitted), including who has authority to grant additional access. None.	

3. DATA MANAGEMENT AND ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Partners	Collection	Curation	Preservation
Foundation Deusto.	☒	☒	☒
Zabala Innovation Consulting S.A.	☐	☐	☐
Town hall of Zamudio	☒	☐	☐
Association of industries cluster environment Euskadi	☐	☐	☐
Green Technologies	☐	☐	☐
Enbio Epe	☐	☐	☐
National Technical University of Athens-NTUA	☒	☐	☐
University of Patras	☒	☐	☐
Dimos Chalandriou	☐	☐	☐
Serious Games Interactive APS	☐	☐	☐
Ars Ambiente SRL	☒	☐	☐
Comune di Seveso	☒	☐	☐
Legambiente Lombardia Onlus	☐	☐	☐
Softline SRL	☐	☐	☐
Moba Mobile Automation AG	☐	☐	☐
EMAC Municipal enterprise environment Cascais	☒	☐	☐
Urban Ecology Agency of Barcelona	☒	☐	☐
Other (please specify):	☐	☐	☐
What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?			
None			

How will these be covered?	
Primary storage medium and location	
☐ University shared or research storage ☐ Secure facility from a data provider ☐ Physical storage ☐ Cloud platforms (e.g. Github) ☒ Last resort platforms (e.g. Zenodo)	☐ Academic research network platforms (e.g. ResearchGate). ☐ Institutional open data repositories (e.g. CKAN based) ☐ Other (please specify):
Link regarding to data repositories: http://www.re3data.org/	
Data curation processes	
Please briefly describe the management of data throughout its life cycle. The data will be updated, modified and corrected during the monitoring carried out in the project	
How will long-term preservation and access be assured?	
Please briefly describe how the data will be preserved after the end of the project. Stored in ZENODO	
Regularity of backups and data performed. Replicas in other different places (if any)	
For D1.4, no backup of data is needed, as it's not a dynamic database.	
File management versioning	
☐ Unnecessary (i.e. overwrite original file) ☐ Control version software (e.g. Git, please specify):	☒ Date/version number in filename/folder ☐ Other (please specify):

4. ETHICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS

Ethical aspect (If know)
☐ No ☒ Yes (briefly describe): Aspects regarding informed consent in data collection and information protection in data storage and access. (Fulfilment of Ethical requirements are detailed in D9.1 – D9.7). The census data to perform the accessibility and proximity analysis have been anonymised
Legal aspect (If know)
☒ No ☐ Yes (briefly describe):

5. OTHER ASPECTS

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